

MEASURING THE IMPACT OF MICROFINANCE ON SOCIAL ENHANCEMENT OF WOMEN: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

During 2011, market commentators predicted the end of India's microfinance market. DAY-NRLM is being implemented across the country in a mission mode since 2011 with the aim to bring at least one-woman member from each rural poor household, as per the Socio-Economic Caste Census (SECC) 2011 data and process of Participatory Identification of Poor (PIP), into the fold of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) and to support them to take up economic activities. As on 31st January, 2025 about 10.05 crore Women households have been mobilized into 90.90 lakh Self Help Groups (SHGs). The extensive study of existing literature indicates that several studies have been undertaken either by individuals, institutions or research agencies to review the prospects of the microfinance and socio-economic status of women. So far, scholarly evaluations of microfinance's impact have overwhelmingly focused on measuring the economic empowerment of group members and their families. Comparatively few studies examine microfinance's social impact, and these have relied solely on measuring the social empowerment of individual group members. Though the agencies examined the socio-economic impact of the programme, they were not comprehensive and complete in their approach. As a matter of fact, contributions made in this regard by individual academicians and researchers are limited in scope and their attention was focused either on social factors or on economic conditions of the self-help group members. Further, no study was conducted in Malenadu regions in linking credit with Social conditions of women SHGs in the region. To fill the gap in research, the present study has been undertaken to encompass various dimensions of the microfinance in respect of improvement in social conditions of women SHG members, specifically in Malenadu regions in the state of Karnataka, India.

INTRODUCTION

Times immemorial, it has been believed that, the 'Self-help is the best help'! 'Unity is strength'! 'United people stand, divided they fall'. There is also popular story of the birds caught in a net. They could only escape as a group but not with an individual effort. The imperative being the collective efforts has always been strong. So is the case with a bundle of sticks as against a single one. The SHGs show us how unity is strength. They show us how self-help could be the best help.

Self Help Groups are informal associations of people ranging between 10 and 20 in numbers. It typically comprises a group of micro entrepreneurs having homogenous social and economic backgrounds; voluntarily coming together to save regular small sums

of money, mutually agreeing to contribute to a common fund and to meet their emergency needs on the basis of mutual help.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Rural women are silent workers in the rural economy. Very often, their contribution goes unnoticed. They are free labor in the family and works for the agricultural lands of rural families. This work of them not only goes unnoticed but also does not earn her the respect she deserves to get. The realities of rural life in India are difficult to comprehend. The lives of most people in rural India have hardly improved (Abraham George, 2001). As a result, women's economic, social, and cultural rights are routinely violated in housing, education, and employments, as well as their right to food or a means of subsistence (Ngwakwe, 2002).

Women are considered central to the success of poverty alleviation efforts. Because of inequities in education, levels of skill, social constraints on their mobility and the attitudinal and institutional barriers to which their behavior is subjected, women in households with an income below the absolute or relative threshold of poverty remain poorer than men of the same households (Soofia Mumtaz, 2000).

Women empowerment is important in order to make use of humankind's full potential; 70 percent of the world's poor are women (Khan and Noreen, 2012). The failures of the formal financial systems resulted in the development of the concept of microfinance. Poor people have continuously been denied access to financial services and in an attempt to reach these people, microfinance emerged as a possible solution (Brau & Woller, 2004).

Sridevi Samineni (2023). highlighted that, in the light of empirical evidence, a wide variation in the outreach of microfinance intervention to the poor women is observed across the regions of the country. Women's empowerment is seen as the progressive index for development. Debadutta Kumar Panda (2009), pointed out that there is a positive impact of Self- Help Groups based microfinance on income, employment, savings, migration reduction, literacy position, household decision-making, participation in PRIs and micro-enterprise development of the women SHG members.

Another study by Mohammad Kamal Hossain (2012) indicates a significant improvement in the sanitary condition and potable water. Mark M. Pitt, Shahidur R. Khandker and Jennifer Cartwright (2006). noticed that Credit programs lead to women taking a greater role in household decision making, having greater access to financial and economic resources, having greater social networks, having greater bargaining power vis-a`-vis their husbands, and having greater freedom of mobility.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is **descriptive** in nature and it's based on **Ex post facto study / after-the-fact research**. To assess the changes in social conditions of Self Help Group member's **qualitative method** has been used.

Sample Design

The respondents are selected on the basis of **multi-stage stratified random sampling technique** comprising Women self-help groups functioning in Karnataka State in India. In Karnataka state, Districts that covers Malenadu regions and the Taluks that are associated with Malenadu region. At the Taluks level Mandals in which SHG linked schemes are functioning and respondents from the selected group. The list of SHGs who have obtained finance in each selected Mandals is obtained from the Karnataka State Co-Operative Apex Bank Ltd, Bangalore.

Sample Size

The sample size consists of 250 respondents that include 200 beneficiaries and 50 non-beneficiaries of microfinance. The sample size is restricted to 250 due to time and resources constraints.

Period of the Study

As the study aims at evaluating the performance of the microfinance in the 'pre' and 'post' framework, it is felt that the samples should cover the time period since inception of Micro finance in Malenadu region, Karnataka till 2024.

To examine the impact of micro finance on social conditions, the time period has been classified in to two stages. First stage includes the loan availed period and the subsequent stages were used to examine the impact of microfinance. In this context, the reference period has been considered from 2006 to 2010, 2011 to 2015, 2016 to 2020 and 2021 onwards.

Social Indicators

The Social indicators that were used to test the effect of microfinance towards women SHG members were listed with parameters such as Self Confidence, Skills, Social Awareness etc. These parameters have further sub factors, which show the Social upliftment.

The scale items that were analysed are scaled responses (Likert scaled items) and were subjected to Cronbach's alpha, which in reality means Kuder-Richardson 20. It is to be noted that though the KR-20 is used for scaled responses, the formula for Cronbach's alpha builds on the KR-20 formula to make it suitable for items with scaled responses and continuous variables as the underlying math is simpler for items with dichotomous response options. After running the test, the same α coefficient and other similar output is achieved and the results are interpreted of the output in the same way.

Profile of Women Respondents

Out of 200 beneficiaries, 82.125 percent were Hindus, 9.5 percent were Muslims, 7.25 percent were Christians and 1.125 percent was others. Further, it is observed that most of the beneficiaries (82 percent) were from Hindus and remaining 18 percent from other religion.

Out of 200 beneficiaries 12.625 percent were SC caste, 26.625 percent were ST, 46.25 percent were OBC, 6.625 percent were GM and 7.875 percent were from other caste. Majority of the beneficiaries (47 percent) and non-beneficiaries (48 percent) were found in the age group of 36-45 years. It may be inferred that majority of respondents were clustered in the working age groups. It is noticed that the illiterates are found more in numbers in case of beneficiaries rather than non-beneficiaries as the percentage is 35.5 percent.

The illiterates were attracted much towards microfinance to improve their standard of living instead of literates whose percentage is very less as noticed from the data. The most of the sample respondents were married constituting 93 percent among the beneficiaries and 94.5 percent among non-beneficiaries.

The occupational pattern shows that agriculture is the main occupation of the beneficiary respondents. Agriculture is the predominant sector for microfinance beneficiaries of the Malenadu region, which employs nearly 47.125 percent of the total respondents.

DATA ANALYSIS

Confidence Level to Manage Financial Issues:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Manna- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	586.49	11206.500	-19.655	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	156.53			
Total	250				

Confidence Level to Interact with Bank Executives:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Manna- Whitne U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	585.09	12328.000	-19.355	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	162.14			
Total	250				

Physical Mobility at Social Places:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	585.83	11737.500	-19.512	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	159.19			
Total	250				

Confidence Level to Participate in the Local Government:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	585.39	12091.000	-19.414	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	160.96			
Total	250				

Confidence Level to Participate in Community Development Programmes:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	585.67	11868.000	-19.478	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	159.84			
Total	250				

Communication Skills:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	587.04	10767.000	-19.777	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	154.34			
Total	250				

Business Skills:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	587.08	10740.000	-19.756	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	154.20			
Total	250				

Financial Skills:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	587.75	10201.500	-19.910	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	151.51			
Total	250				

Social Recognition:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	588.74	9409.000	-20.136	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	147.55			
Total	250				

Knowledge of Social Awareness:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	585.18	12254.000	-19.351	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	161.77			
Total	250				

Ability to Handle Social Exploitations:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	586.38	11300.000	-19.678	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	157.00			
Total	250				

Respect in the Family:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	586.64	11087.000	-19.681	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	155.94			
Total	250				

Gender Equality in the Family:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	583.41	13670.000	-18.976	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	168.85			
Total	250				

Access to Hygienic Sanitation Facilities:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	587.47	10427.500	-19.872	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	152.64			
Total	250				

Hygienic Drinking Water Availability:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	589.35	8920.000	-20.263	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	145.10			
Total	250				

Job Securities:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	586.80	10961.000	-19.722	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	155.31			
Total	250				

Reduction in Dependency and Decision-Making Power:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	586.71	11034.500	-19.695	.000
Non-Beneficiaries	50	155.67			
Total	250				

Improvement in the Accommodation:

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	Mann- Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Beneficiaries	200	586.50	1150.000	-19.651	.000*
Non-Beneficiaries	50	156.50			
Total	250				

INTERPRETATION & DISCUSSION

- a. **Confidence level to managing financial issues:** There is a significant difference in the confidence level of managing financial issues of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is observed that after the microfinance period, there is no significant difference in the confidence level of beneficiaries to manage the financial issues among the groups. However, the beneficiaries who were associated with the microfinance schemes from the year 2006-125 had improved significantly in their confidence level to manage the financial issues in the post period. Mean Rank of beneficiaries is 586.49, which are much higher than that of the non-beneficiaries i.e 156.53. This shows microfinance has helped the beneficiaries to improve their confidence level to manage financial issues.
- b. **Confidence level to interact with bank executives:** there is a significant difference in the confidence level to interact with bank executives by the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. 185 respondents showed positive changes in their confidence level to interact with bank executives and 15 respondents could not find

any difference. It is observed that after the microfinance period there is no significant difference in the confidence level of beneficiaries to interact with bank executives among the groups. However, the beneficiaries who are associated with the microfinance schemes from the year 2011-505 had improved significantly in their confidence level to interact with bank executives in the post period. There is a significant difference in the confidence level of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries to interact with bank executives in the post period.

- c. Physical mobility in Social Places:** There is a significant difference in the physical mobility in social places of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is observed that after the microfinance period there is no significant difference in the physical mobility at social places of beneficiaries among the groups. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 585.83, which are much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 159.19. This shows microfinance has helped the beneficiaries to improve their physical mobility in social places compare to non- beneficiaries.
- d. Confidence level to participate in the local government:** 184 respondents showed positive changes in their confidence level to participate in the local government and 16 respondents could not find any difference. It is observed that after the microfinance period there is a significant difference in the confidence level of beneficiaries to participate in local government among the groups. It is also noticed that beneficiaries who joined microfinance scheme in 2006-125 has less confidence level to participate in local government compare to other groups. There is a significant difference in the confidence level of beneficiaries and non- beneficiaries to participate in the local government in the post period.
- e. Participation in community development progammes:** There is a significant difference in the confidence level of beneficiaries to participate in the community development progammes among the groups. Confidence level of participation in the community development progammes is not depending on the year of association with the microfinance schemes. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 585.67, which are much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 159.84. This shows microfinance has helped the beneficiaries to improve their confidence level to participate in the community development progammes compare to non- beneficiaries.
- f. Communication Skills:** The beneficiaries of microfinance have recorded a satisfactory increase in their communication skills. 187 respondents showed positive changes and 13 respondents showed no changes in their communication skills. It is noticed that mean rank 437.51 from the period 2021 onwards is much higher than any other period of association. This shows improvement of communication skills is not depending on the year of association with the microfinance scheme. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 587.04, which are much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 154.34.
- g. Business Skills:** There is a significant difference in the business skills of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. 185 respondents showed positive changes in their business skills and 15 respondents could not find any

difference in their business skills in the post period. Improvement of business skills is also not depending on the year of association with the microfinance schemes. Microfinance has helped the beneficiaries to improve their business skills compare to non-beneficiaries.

- h. Financial skills:** There is a significant difference in the financial skills of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. The beneficiaries who are associated with the microfinance schemes from the year 2021 onwards had improved significantly in their financial skills in the post period. It is noticed that mean rank 443.59 from the period 2021 onwards is much higher than any other period of association. There is a significant difference in the financial skills of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in the post period. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 587.75, which are much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 151.51.
- i. Social recognition:** There is a significant difference in the social recognition of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is also noticed that beneficiaries who joined microfinance scheme in 2016-2020 has less improvement in the social recognition compare to other groups. It is observed that there is a significant difference in the social recognition of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in the post period.
- j. Social awareness:** There is a significant difference in the knowledge of social awareness of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is clear that 187 respondents showed positive changes in their knowledge of social awareness and 13 respondents could not find any difference. It is noticed that mean rank 447.15 from the period 2021 onwards is much higher than any other period of association. This shows improvement of knowledge of social awareness is not depending on the year of association with the microfinance schemes. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 585.18, which are much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 161.77.
- k. Ability to handle social exploitations:** There is a significant difference in the ability to handle social exploitations of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is noticed that mean rank 434.00 from the period 2021 onwards is much higher than any other period of association. Microfinance has helped beneficiaries to handle and to come out of the social exploitations like abuse, violence, drugs, alcoholism etc.
- l. Respect in the family:** It is clear that 184 respondents showed positive changes in their respect in their family and 2 respondents showed negative changes. It is also noticed that 14 respondents could not find any difference in the respect. It is observed that after the microfinance period there is no significant difference in the respect in the family of beneficiaries among the groups. There is a significant difference in respect in the family of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in the post period.
- m. Gender equality:** There is a significant difference in the gender equality in the family of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is clear that 187 respondents showed positive changes in their gender equality in their family and 13

respondents could not find any difference. It is noticed that beneficiaries who joined microfinance scheme in 2006-125 has less improvement in the gender equality in the family compare to other groups. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 583.41, which are much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 168.85.

- n. Access to hygienic sanitation facilities:** There is a significant difference in the access to hygienic sanitation facilities of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is noticed that mean rank 417.59 from the period 2021 onwards is higher than any other period of association followed by mean rank 416.82 from the period 2006-125. There is a significant difference in access to hygienic sanitation facilities of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in the post period.
- o. Hygienic drinking water availability:** It is clear that 182 respondents showed positive changes in their hygienic drinking water availability and 18 respondents could not find any difference. It is noticed that mean rank 432.60 from the period 2021 onwards is much higher than any other period of association. This shows improvement of hygienic drinking water availability is not depending on the year of association with the microfinance schemes. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 589.35 which is much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 145.10 this shows microfinance has helped the beneficiaries to improve their hygienic drinking water availability.
- p. Job securities:** There is a significant difference in the job securities for the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is observed that after the microfinance period there is a significant difference in the job securities among the groups. It is observed that there is a significant difference in job securities for the beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in the post period. Mean rank of beneficiaries is 586.80, which are much higher than the non-beneficiaries i.e 155.31.
- q. Reduction in dependency and decision making power:** It is clear that 179 respondents showed positive changes in their reduction in dependency and decision making power. It is noticed that mean rank 438.71 from the period 2021 onwards is much higher than any other period of association. This shows improvement of reduction in dependency and decision-making power is not depending on the year of association with the microfinance schemes. There is a significant difference in reduction in dependency and decision making power of the beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in the post period.
- r. Improvement in the accommodation:** There is a significant difference in the improvement in the accommodation of the beneficiaries in the pre and post period of microfinance. It is noticed that mean rank 431.92 from the period 2021 onwards is higher than any other period of association followed by mean rank 403.62 from the period 2010-2015. This shows improvement of improvement in the accommodation is not depending on the year of association with the microfinance schemes. There is a significant difference in improvement in the accommodation of the beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries in the post period.

CONCLUSION

Self-help Groups Bank linkage programme brings positive socio-economic changes in the lives of the Women SHG members and also become a platform where the members were able to access the information on various issues like rural Employment Guarantee Scheme, Panchayat Procedures, Public Distribution Systems etc. Thus, by this study, it can be concluded that the rural women's have been greatly benefited by Microfinance. The rural deprived now feel that they can also be associates in the process of rural development by joining the microfinance. The training of the members by the Govt and NGOs had increased their confidence, restored self-importance and improved their social concern about the neighbors. This study has also indicated that even though the members have joined the SHGs for various reasons, all of them have one common goal, which is seeking a better standard of living through a better organization that works for their benefits. The SHG can contribute to changes in economic conditions, social status, decision making and increases women in outdoor activities. SHG not only changes the outer form of a community or a society but also the social institutions as well as ideas of the people living in the society.

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